

Quality Models and Quality Attributes for Open Educational Resources: a systematic mapping

Myke Morais de Oliveira, Leo Natan Paschoal, and Ellen Francine Barbosa
Instituto de Ciências Matemáticas e de Computação (ICMC)
Universidade de São Paulo
São Carlos, São Paulo, Brasil

This document is intended to present the protocol that was used to conduct the systematic mapping that was published in the 51th edition of the Frontiers in Education (FIE) conference in 2021.

1. Objective

The main objective of this study is to provide a broad and detailed overview of the main quality attributes and quality models for Open Educational Resources (OER). For this purpose, we conducted a systematic mapping to identify and analyze the main approaches used to define and evaluate quality attributes and quality models for OER.

2. Elaboration of research questions

The research questions aim to contemplate the aspects involving quality models and quality attributes for OER. They are:

- **RQ1)** What are the quality models and quality attributes proposed for OER?
- **RQ2)** How have these quality models or quality attributes been established for OER?
- **RQ3)** How have quality models or quality attributes for OER been evaluated?

3. Data sources for research

With the intention of contemplating what has been developed in the international literature, we have selected the main data sources for analysis and extraction of primary studies. They are:

- ACM Digital Library (<http://portal.acm.org>);
- Engineering Village (<https://www.engineeringvillage.com/search/quick.url>);
- Elsevier (Science Direct) (<http://www.sciencedirect.com>);
- IEEE Xplore (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>);
- Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com>);
- Web of Science (<https://webofknowledge.com>);

4. Keywords and synonyms

Keywords: open educational resources, quality models, quality attributes.

English synonyms: {open, free}+{educational resource, learning content, learning object, educational module, learning material, courseware}, {quality}.

5. Search string

Inflection and language	String
Singular String	((("open" OR "free") AND ("OER" OR "educational resource" OR "learning object" OR "educational module" OR "learning material" OR "learning content" OR "courseware"))) AND ("quality"))
Plural String	((("open" OR "free") AND ("OERs" OR "educational resources" OR "learning objects" OR "educational modules" OR "learning materials" OR "coursewares"))) AND ("quality"))

6. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for primary studies

Inclusion Criteria (IC)	Exclusion Criteria (EC)
IC-1: The primary study addresses a quality model for OER.	EC-1: It is a technical report, a simple/expanded abstract, a presentation, a proceedings of a conference or workshop, a working in progress, a short paper, a secondary study or a tertiary study.
IC-2: The primary study addresses one or more quality attribute for OER.	EC-2: The language used in the primary study is different from English.
	EC-3: The full text of the primary study is unavailable.
	EC-4: The primary study does not address quality models or/and quality attributes for OER.
	EC-5: The study is a previous version of a more complete study on the same research, with the same authors.

7. String adaptation for each data source

7.1. Searches in English on 05/16/2020

Search Database	Search String	Outcome
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(((("open" OR "free") AND ("OER" OR "educational resource" OR "learning object" OR "educational module" OR "learning material" OR "learning content" OR "courseware" OR "OERs" OR "educational resources" OR "learning objects" OR "educational modules" OR "learning materials" OR "coursewares"))) AND ("quality"))	771

ACM Digital Library	[[Abstract: "open"] OR [Abstract: "free"]] AND [[Abstract: "oer"] OR [Abstract: "educational resource"] OR [Abstract: "learning object"] OR [Abstract: "educational module"] OR [Abstract: "learning material"] OR [Abstract: "learning content"] OR [Abstract: "courseware"] OR [Abstract: "oers"] OR [Abstract: "educational resources"] OR [Abstract: "learning objects"] OR [Abstract: "educational modules"] OR [Abstract: "learning materials"] OR [Abstract: "coursewares"]] AND [Abstract: "quality"]		45
IEEE Xplore	<i>((("All Metadata": "open" OR "free") AND ("All Metadata": "OER" OR "educational resource" OR "learning object" OR "educational module" OR "learning material" OR "learning content" OR "courseware" "OERs" OR "educational resources" OR "learning objects" OR "educational modules" OR "learning materials" OR "coursewares") AND ("All Metadata": "quality")))</i>		132
Web of Science	Singular	TS=((("open" OR "free") AND ("OER" OR "educational resource" OR "learning object" OR "educational module" OR "learning material" OR "learning content" OR "courseware")) AND ("quality"))	351
	Plural	TS=((("open" OR "free") AND ("OERs" OR "educational resources" OR "learning objects" OR "educational modules" OR "learning materials" OR "coursewares")) AND ("quality"))	427
ScienceDirect	Singular	Title, abstract, keywords: ((("open" OR "free") AND ("OER" OR "educational resource" OR "learning object" OR "educational module" OR "learning material" OR "learning content" OR "courseware")) AND ("quality"))	689

	Plural	Title, abstract, keywords: (((("open" OR "free") AND ("OERs" OR "educational resources" OR "learning objects" OR "educational modules" OR "learning materials" OR "coursewares")) AND ("quality"))	43
Engineering Village		found in Compendex & Knovel for 1884-2020:((((("open" OR "free") AND ("OER" OR "educational resource" OR "learning object" OR "educational module" OR "learning material" OR "learning content" OR "courseware" OR "OERs" OR "educational resources" OR "learning objects" OR "educational modules" OR "learning materials" OR "coursewares")) AND ("quality"))))	412

As can be seen in the table above, we separated the search string into singular and plural in the Web of Science and ScienceDirect databases because there were a very large number of studies in areas that were not related (e.g., chemistry, physics). So, we decided to separate the search string and then join the results, leaving out duplicate studies. The searches returned a **total** of **2870** studies, of which **1114** were **duplicates**. Thus, we have **1756** remaining studies for the first selection in which titles, abstracts and keywords will be read.